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Impact Of School Inspectors And Teachers’ Effectiveness In Curriculum Implementation In Lower Basic Education In Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of school inspectors on teachers’ effectiveness in curriculum implementation in lower basic education in Gwagwalada Area Council, FCT -Nigeria. Two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study was one thousand and fifty-nine (1059) public lower basic schools’ teachers in Gwagwalada Area Council. The sample size was two hundred and twenty four (224) teachers selected from public basic schools in Gwagwalada Area Council. Proportional sampling techniques was used in the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. The research instrument used for the study was a researcher designed questionnaire titled Impact of School Inspectors on Teachers Effectiveness Questionnaire (ISITEQ). The instrument was pilot tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMC) and had a reliability index of 0.87. The instrument was validated by three lecturers in the field of curriculum. Data collected were analysed using simple percentage, mean and standard deviation while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of teachers’ lesson planning effectiveness for curriculum implementation. In addition, it was observed that there is significant difference on the impact of school inspection by school inspectors and teachers’ effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council. The findings also revealed that the issue of gender influence did not arise in curriculum implementation. Based on the findings, the researcher therefore recommends that government, school inspectors and teachers should employ all opportunities available for the proper implementation of the curriculum.

Keywords: Inspectors, Teachers, Curriculum, Implementation

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process that prepares an individual from birth through life and makes the individual a useful and happy member of the society the individual belongs to. Education provides an individual the total development the individual needs to become an asset and not a liability to the society. The total development of an individual includes the physical, social, emotional and spiritual development. Thus, education is regarded as an important agent of change due to its role in social, economic, political and technological development (Molagun, 2006; Akpan, 2008). This is evident in the steps various countries have taken in providing quality education through meaningful investment in the education sector.

In Nigeria, basic education serves as the crucial stepping stone for pupils to advance to secondary school and eventually to tertiary institutions. In 2016 major reforms and innovations were introduced into the Nigerian educational system as stated in the National Policy on Education, that lower basic education is the education given in institutions for children aged 6 to 9 years. Since the Nigerian education system is built upon it, the lower basic level is a key to the success or failure of the whole system. The duration for the lower basic education shall be three years (Imam & Mohammed, 2017). The objectives of lower basic education are to: inculcate permanent literacy and numeracy, and ability to communicate effectively; lay a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking, give citizenship education as a basis for effective participation and contribution to the life of the society; mould the character and develop sound attitude and morals in the child; develop in the child the ability to adapt to the child's changing environment; give the child opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable the child function effectively in the society within the limits of the child's capacity; provide the child with basic tools for further educational advancement, including preparation for trades and crafts of the locality (Ola-Alani & Olayiwola, 2022). Invariably, realization of these objectives depends on numerous factors including inspection.

Accordingly, inspection is the form of evaluation, which involves the measurement, testing and evaluation of educational activities in school systems for the purpose of improving the standard and quality of education programs offered (Hofer et al., 2020). Similarly, school inspection is basic and fundamental to the attainment of set objectives. The role of inspectors of education cannot be over-emphasised hence the need to ensure that the quality of education received meets a required minimum standard. This provides the basis for inspection in education and of course at the lower basic level (Gardezi et al. 2023).

The Inspector holds major position in the programme of teachers' improvement through effective and efficient supervision of teachers' performance using various supervisory techniques. The inspector is thus faced with the responsibility of supervising teachers generally, with a view to improving their effectiveness, make recommendations and also manage both human and material resources towards achieving the educational goals and objectives (Jeremiah & Queensoap, 2024). The inspectors as the evaluator of the school, is the architect of all activities in the school, and the academic achievement of students largely, depends on the performance of teachers. Thus, it becomes important that inspectors' supervisory functions must be adequate to affect the performance of teachers (Brown et al., 2016). One significant area affected by school inspections is teachers' lesson planning.

Lesson planning is a crucial component of effective teaching, serving as the roadmap for what students need to learn and how it will be accomplished during class. Lesson planning allows teachers to align instructional objectives with standards, organize content, and structure classroom activities (Suwarma & Apriyani, 2022). Clearly, well-structured lesson plans contribute to improved student outcomes by providing clear goals and structured learning experiences (Brilliananda, Herwin. & Praheto, 2025). School inspections have a significant impact on teachers' lesson planning, driving improvements in accountability, professional development, and focus on student outcomes (Brown et al., 2016). Effective lesson planning is linked to better data-driven decision-making, allowing educators to tailor their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of students thereby aiding the implementation of the curriculum.

Statement of the Problem

Despite significant investments in pupils' education by parents and the government, academic outcomes have been disappointing. The poor performance of pupils in lower basic schools remains a major concern for all stakeholders in the Nigerian education sector. School inspection is intended to be a tool for the government to monitor schools and support teachers in their teaching and learning processes. However, many teachers fail to teach effectively, and do not maintain proper school records. Given that school inspectors are supposed to oversee and guide teachers, it raises questions about why teachers neglect record-keeping, do not plan lessons properly, are not dedicated to their duties, and struggle with classroom management, mutual coexistence with pupils and overcrowded classrooms. Therefore, this study aims to determine the impact of school inspection on teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation in lower basic schools in the Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to find out the impact of school inspection on teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic level of education in Gwagwalada Area Council. Specifically, the study sought to attain the following objectives:

- (i) determine the impact of school inspection on teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic level of education in Gwagwalada Area Council
- (ii) determine the impact of effectiveness of lesson planning by teachers for curriculum implementation at the in lower basic schools in Gwagwalada Area Council.

Research Questions

To guide the study the following research questions were formulated

- i. What is the impact of school inspection on teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic level of education in Gwagwalada Area Council?
- ii. What is the impact of lesson planning on teachers' curriculum implementation effectiveness at the Lower basic school in Gwagwalada Area council?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated to guide the study

- Ho₁ There is no significant difference in the mean of score of impact of inspection and teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council FCT based on location.
- Ho₂ There is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female teachers' lesson planning effectiveness for curriculum implementation at lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council FCT.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is anchored on the systems theory. The systems theory is postulated by Ludwig Von Bertallarfy (1947). It considers every system a subsystem and every subsystem a system. System theory focuses on the relations between the parts of a system (i.e. Basic school system). Systems theory explains the arrangement of and relations between the parts, how they work together as a whole. The way the subsystems (Inspectors subsystem, teacher subsystem, student subsystem, curriculum subsystem, administrative subsystem etc) are organized and how they interact with each other determines the properties of that system.

The systems theory is relevant to this study as it explains the inseparable relationship between inspectors factors and teacher factors (which are embedded in the inspectors subsystem and teacher subsystem) such as the ways lower basic school teachers are inspected, their quantity, quality, teaching methods they adopt, level of motivation, use of instructional materials and their commitment to other subsystems in the school system which includes implementation of the curriculum in all subjects. Through the systems theory, it is made clear that the inspector subsystem and teacher subsystem are key components in achieving desired goals of the multidimensional school system and its disfunctionality or otherwise (functionality) have an immense effect on the activities and functioning of other subsystems.

The quantity and quality of lower basic school inspectors is important for achieving and sustaining school goals and objectives that are instructional in nature. Also, flexibility in inspection methods and by inspectors makes the teaching-learning process or job interaction with teachers worthwhile. This aids in improving the commitment and teaching habits of teachers and their effective performance. When teachers feel motivated, they devote themselves to working actively with the school organization to actualize the goals and objectives that have been planned which includes implementing the curriculum of various subjects.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is descriptive survey design. Also, the design enabled the researcher to make use of a questionnaire in collecting data. The population of this study consisted of all the teachers in the public basic schools in Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory.

There are one thousand and fifty-nine (1059) teachers in all the public lower basic schools in Gwagwalada Area Council. The sample size for this study were 224 (Two hundred and twenty four) certified teachers in the lower basic classes out of one thousand and fifty-nine (1059) teachers certified teachers in the basic schools in Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory. This represents 21% which is large enough for generalization. The teachers were chosen because the teachers meet the teaching requirement and certification in lower basic Schools. Proportional sampling method was used to pick the sample size because of the uneven distribution of lower basic teachers among the schools. This sample size was based on the staff strength of lower basic teachers of the randomly selected schools. The sample of this study was selected from all the one thousand one hundred and twenty teachers of sub-urban and urban schools of the twelve selected schools in Gwagwalada Area Council. The study is designed to cover 224 lower basic teachers in the selected twelve lower basic Schools in Gwagwalada. This is for effective coverage, proper geographical representation and uniform generalizations. The instrument for the study was the Impact of School Inspectors on Teachers Effectiveness Questionnaire (ISITEQ). The 4-point Likert scale of which SA represents strongly agree, A represents agree, D represents disagree and SD represents strongly disagree were used in the questionnaire. The validity of the research instrument was ascertained by the three experts in curriculum department who validated the instrument while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used for reliability of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was done through a pilot test that involved twenty six teachers from two lower basic schools not selected for the study. Split half method was adopted and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to analyse the responses from the instrument. The reliability coefficient index was 0.87 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). This confirmed that the instrument is reliable and thus suitable for further administration. The data required for this study was collected from the respondents through the aid of the research instrument which was analysed statistically using mean and standard deviation for analysis of questionnaire. The research hypotheses were tested using t-test. All the data were analysed with the aid of SPSS. The critical level of significance for acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses is 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the impact of school inspection on teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic level of education in Gwagwalada Area Council?*

Table 1: Impact of Lesson Planning by Teachers in Lower Basic Education School for Curriculum Implementation

		n = 224		
S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I plan my lessons according to topics and the stated objectives for effective implementation of the curriculum	3.62	0.564	Accepted
2	I assess students' knowledge about a topic before beginning a new topic	3.42	0.630	Accepted
3	I use lesson planning as an effective technique to implement the curriculum to students' needs	3.40	0.708	Accepted
4	I analyse objectives and determine if they focus on facts, concepts, or principles	3.25	0.765	Accepted
5	I do not plan for lessons to meet the academic needs of all Students	2.15	0.983	Rejected
Sectional Mean		3.17		

As presented in Table 1, teachers generally reported positive lesson planning practices that support curriculum implementation. The overall sectional mean was 3.17, indicating agreement that lesson planning contributes to effective curriculum delivery. Specifically, respondents agreed that they plan their lessons according to stated objectives (M = 3.62, SD = 0.56), assess students' prior knowledge before introducing new topics (M = 3.42, SD = 0.63), and use lesson planning as an effective technique to meet

students' needs ($M = 3.40$, $SD = 0.71$). Teachers also reported analyzing instructional objectives to determine whether they focus on facts, concepts, or principles ($M = 3.25$, $SD = 0.77$).

However, respondents disagreed with the negatively worded statement, "I do not plan for lessons to meet the academic needs of all students" ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 0.98$), indicating that teachers generally plan lessons to address diverse learners' needs. Based on the descriptive statistics, school inspection appears to have a positive impact on teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic level of education in Gwagwalada Area Council. Teachers demonstrate strong engagement in structured lesson planning, objective analysis, and student-centered instructional practices.

Research Question Two: *How effective are teachers in lesson planning for curriculum implementation at the Lower basic school in Gwagwalada Area council?*

Table 2: Teachers' regularity in lesson planning in Lower Basic School level in Gwagwalada Area council.

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lower Basic level teachers in Gwagwalada Area Council consistently engage in lesson planning	3.49	0.591	Accepted
2	Teachers at the Lower Basic level prioritize lesson planning as an integral part of their teaching routine	3.34	0.657	Accepted
3	Lower Basic level teachers in Gwagwalada Area Council find lesson planning to be a beneficial practice for effective teaching	3.25	0.642	Accepted
4	The school administration provides sufficient support and resources for Lower Basic level teachers to engage in regular lesson planning	3.03	0.792	Accepted
5	The majority of Lower Basic level teachers in Gwagwalada Area Council regularly update and adjust their lesson plans	2.96	0.791	Accepted
Sectional Mean		3.21		

As shown in Table 2, the overall sectional mean was 3.21, indicating a high level of effectiveness in lesson planning among teachers at the Lower Basic level. On a 4-point Likert scale, this sectional mean suggests that respondents generally agreed that lesson planning is regularly and effectively practiced. Teachers reported consistently engaging in lesson planning ($M = 3.49$, $SD = 0.59$), indicating strong regularity in planning practices. They also agreed that lesson planning is prioritized as an integral part of their teaching routine ($M = 3.34$, $SD = 0.66$). Furthermore, respondents perceived lesson planning as beneficial for effective teaching ($M = 3.25$, $SD = 0.64$).

Regarding institutional support, teachers agreed that school administration provides sufficient support and resources to facilitate regular lesson planning ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 0.79$). Additionally, the majority indicated that they regularly update and adjust their lesson plans ($M = 2.96$, $SD = 0.79$), though this item recorded the lowest mean among the accepted statements. The relatively low standard deviations (ranging from 0.59 to 0.79) suggest moderate consistency in responses among participants.

Based on the descriptive statistics, teachers in Lower Basic schools in Gwagwalada Area Council demonstrate strong effectiveness in lesson planning for curriculum implementation. Lesson planning is consistently practiced, valued, and supported institutionally.

Hypothesis 1:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean score of urban and rural impact of inspection and teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council based on the location.

Table 3: Mean Score of the Impact of Inspection and Teachers’ Effectiveness in Curriculum Implementation at Lower Basic Education Level in Gwagwalada Area Council based on the Location.

Location	N	Mean	S D	t-statistic	p-value	Decision
Rural	61	3.74	0.444	1.987	0.048	Significant
Urban	163	3.57	0.598			

As shown on Table 3, an independent samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether a significant difference exists between rural and urban schools regarding the impact of inspection on teachers’ effectiveness in curriculum implementation. Results indicated that teachers in rural schools ($n = 61, M = 3.74, SD = 0.44$) reported slightly higher effectiveness compared to teachers in urban schools ($n = 163, M = 3.57, SD = 0.60$). The difference between the two groups was statistically significant, $t(222) = 1.99, p = 0.048$. Since the *p*-value (0.048) is less than the alpha level of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between rural and urban schools regarding the impact of inspection on teachers’ effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council.

Hypothesis 2:

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female teachers’ lesson planning effectiveness for curriculum implementation at lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council.

Tables 4: Mean Score of Male and Female Teachers’ Lesson planning Effectiveness for Curriculum Implementation at Lower Basic Education Level in Gwagwalada Area Council.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-statistic	p-value	Decision
Male	124	2.93	0.947	1.291	0.198	Not significant
Female	100	3.08	0.787			

An independent samples *t*-test was conducted to determine whether gender differences exist in teachers’ lesson planning effectiveness for curriculum implementation. The results showed that male teachers ($n = 124, M = 2.93, SD = 0.95$) had a slightly lower mean score compared to female teachers ($n = 100, M = 3.08, SD = 0.79$). However, this difference was not statistically significant, $t(222) = 1.29, p = 0.198$. Since the obtained *p*-value (0.198) is greater than the alpha level of .05, the null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference between male and female teachers’ lesson planning effectiveness for curriculum implementation at the lower basic education level in Gwagwalada Area Council.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study indicate that teachers at the lower basic education level demonstrate strong engagement in lesson planning as a central component of effective curriculum implementation. Teachers organize lessons according to clearly stated objectives, assess learners’ prior knowledge before introducing new topics, and align instructional activities with curriculum expectations. They also analyze instructional objectives to determine their emphasis on facts, concepts, or principles, thereby ensuring that teaching remains structured and goal-oriented.

Furthermore, teachers consciously plan lessons to address the diverse academic needs of learners. This reflects professional responsibility and instructional intentionality rather than routine or superficial compliance. Lesson planning is perceived as an essential part of teaching practice and is treated as a consistent professional obligation. The provision of administrative support and resources also appears to strengthen teachers’ capacity to engage in regular and meaningful lesson preparation.

When differences based on gender were examined, the findings revealed no meaningful variation in lesson planning effectiveness between male and female teachers. Both groups demonstrated comparable commitment to structured instructional planning and curriculum alignment. This suggests that effectiveness in lesson

planning is shaped more by professional standards, training, and supervisory practices than by gender-related factors.

Generally, these findings suggest that school inspection plays a reinforcing role in promoting accountability, preparedness, and curriculum fidelity. Through monitoring and supervisory feedback, inspection appears to sustain teachers' commitment to systematic lesson planning and effective instructional delivery across the lower basic education level.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that school inspection contributes positively to improving teachers' effectiveness in curriculum implementation at the lower basic education level. Sustained, supportive, and context-sensitive inspection practices are therefore essential for maintaining instructional standards and enhancing educational quality within the Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the major findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Teachers should embrace school inspection in basic schools as it improves teachers' effectiveness especially in lower basic schools.
- ii. Comprehensive Seminars, workshops, symposia and conferences should be organised at national and local levels for lower basic teachers to expose them to the skills and competencies required in curriculum implementation.
- iii. Lessons should be developed by teachers to incorporate topics with specific objectives as stipulated in the curriculum for teachers' effectiveness in teaching/learning;
- iv. Stakeholders in education should not consider gender as a major criterion for curriculum implementation in lower basic schools as there was no gender difference in teachers' effectiveness based on gender.
- v. Lower basic school teachers should explore all the opportunities offered by school inspectors for teachers' effectiveness as it concerns curriculum implementation.
- vi. Emphasis should be placed on the importance of school inspection as it concerns teachers' effectiveness to ensure that teachers' effectiveness lead to the implementation of the curriculum

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